

Development of Abaca/Furan Green Composites

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SUMMARY

The mechanical performance of continuous abaca fiber-reinforced furan-based green composites was evaluated. Alkali treatment was done to improve fiber-matrix adhesion, and the fiber sheets were combined with furan by hand lay-up method. The composite's strength was then measured and morphological study of the fracture surface was done.

Keywords: abaca, furan, green composites

INTRODUCTION

In the field of process engineering, fiber reinforced polymeric composites are mainly utilized as linings of tanks, equipment and pipelines. Thermosetting polymer resins such as polyester and vinyl ester resins have been extensively used in producing corrosion-resistant storage vessels that have long service lives and capable of handling various chemicals, both in liquid and gaseous forms, and reinforcements such as glass fibers are incorporated in order to improve their mechanical performance. Among the few thermosetting polymers used in the manufacture of reinforced thermosetting plastic (RTP) laminates, furan resin has been found to possess high chemical and heat resistances, making it suitable for chemical tanks, vessels and pipes [1]. The main disadvantage of using furan is its brittleness, which is the reason why glass fibers are incorporated to this resin to significantly improve its mechanical strength. Recently, however, since glass fibers are not only expensive to produce but are also not environment-friendly, natural fibers such as kenaf, jute and abaca are being tapped as viable alternative reinforcements. Many researches have already reported that these cellulose-based fibers have already been successfully utilized in reinforcing thermoset resins for different applications in the manufacturing and construction industries.

Natural fiber-reinforced (NFR) composites have been consistently gaining attention in the manufacturing industries due to growing environmental concerns. The use of these cellulose-based materials over traditional reinforcements offers several advantages: acceptable specific strengths, low cost, potential energy recovery and biodegradability [2]. It also aids to promote the use of renewable materials, and offers great potential to alleviate our withstanding problem regarding CO₂ emission [3]. The fabrication of these green composites has been finding an increasing number of applications in the production of engineering materials and in the manufacture of commercial goods. Many researches on various chemical treatments of natural fibers are currently and extensively being undertaken to continuously find methods on improving the performance of NFR composites in hopes of making them comparable to that of GFR composites.

This research aims to promote bio-based structural materials such as abaca/furan composites. Development of novel NFR composite materials is one of the many current research interests in the continuing study of green composites to date. The primary objective of such research is to measure the performance of such materials in order to establish proper application and assess their viability as substitutes to the traditional glass fiber-reinforced plastic (GFRP) composites, and discussed in this paper are the initial results obtained from the early developmental stages of this research.

Furan Resin

Furan resin is a condensate of furfuryl alcohol, which can be synthesized from agricultural byproducts such as corn cobs, rice hulls, etc. In the presence of an acid catalyst, furfuryl alcohol yields a resinous product that exhibit excellent resistance to most acids, alkalis and solvents, with the exception of strong oxidizing agents such as peroxides and very strong acids, as well as a strong heat resistance.

As one of the most stable thermosetting plastics, furan resin is highly resistant to biodegradation; however, since it is synthesized from agricultural byproducts, this bio-based polymer resin still offers a certain degree of environment friendliness. The use for production of such sustainable materials, combined with its excellent corrosion resistance, makes furan one of the major commercially available resin mortars and chemical linings [4]. Currently, it is used for acid-brick lining, sand binder for mold casting, and as a precursor for carbon fiber and graphite.

Figure 1. Common challenges in the fabrication of abaca/furan composites: (a) visible cracking/de-bonding and (b) warping of the laminate.

On the down side, the use of furan laminates is restricted due to the limited available data on furan's mechanical properties, apart from those provided by the resin manufacturer. This reduces the design engineer's ability to consider furan as a material of construction for fabricating process equipment. Another reason for the lack of extensive use of furan is the problem associated with condensation polymers. For every mole of crosslink formed during furan's curing, one mole of water is evolved in vapor form (due to the elevated curing temperature and the reaction's exothermic nature) [5]. When curing is done improperly, the water release may cause some serious problems with the FRP fabrication, from warping to cracking and interfacial de-bonding (as shown in Figure 1). The loss of water also causes the laminate to shrink during curing, as well as loss of ductility, which poses an additional challenge to the FRP fabricator.

Abaca Fiber

Abaca, or Manila hemp, is typically harvested as long, continuous fiber bundles- about 2 to 4 meters for technical grade fibers [6]. A member of the banana family native to the Philippines and parts of Indonesia and Central America, the abaca tree (*Musa textilis Nee*) is abundantly grown all year-round for its leaf fibers, which is considered as one of the strongest among the natural fibers [7]. Abaca offers great potential in industrial applications due to its high tensile and specific flexural strength, rot and salt resistance, and great year-round abundance [8]. This makes the highly lignocellulosic fiber suitable for producing ropes and large fishing nets- setting the cordage industry as its primary consumer [9]. Other major industrial and commercial applications of abaca fiber are in the pulp and paper industry and the handicraft industry.

Also, its natural fiber length allows the production of continuous fiber-reinforced composites, which exhibit better mechanical performance than short fiber composites. Recently, abaca fibers are utilized in the manufacture of continuous fiber composites currently used for automobile parts [10].

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Furan resin (Hitafuran V-304, Hitachi Chemical Co., Ltd.) was supplied along with the curing agent (A3, an alkylbenzene sulfonic acid solution). The furan had the following properties: specific gravity 1.2–1.23 (20°C); viscosity 85–1.45 cP (30°C), and 46–54% non-volatile matter. The raw abaca fiber bundles were obtained from a local fibercraft vendors in Manila, Philippines.

Figure 2. Raw abaca fiber bundles (a) are cut (b) and treated with NaOH solution in a reaction set-up with heating mantle, temperature controller and mechanical stirrer (c).

Fiber Preparation

The dried abaca fibers were cut to 20 cm. lengths and treated with 5wt% NaOH solution at 80°C and 15 rpm in a reaction vessel set-up as shown in Figure 2. The treated fibers are then cooled down to room temperature before washing with 5wt% HCl solution, then by running water. The washed fibers are then arranged and pressed into unidirectional fiber sheets at 10 MPa and 50°C for 5 hours. After compression, the fiber

sheets were air dried to remove any excess moisture, then kept dry by placing inside a drying oven at 50°C.

FRP Specimen Preparation

The fiber sheets were impregnated with the furan mixture containing 1% curing agent by hand lay-up method. The matrix resin was added slowly to the fiber sheets placed in a 2-mm thick stainless steel mold, which was initially treated with a mold release agent (Daifree GA-6010, Daikin Industries, Ltd.), using a roller to assist with incorporating the furan with the fiber sheets.

The three-step curing procedure of the furan FRP was done in reference to the method presented by Thygesen, et al. [11]: first, the mixture was compressed at a constant pressure of 20 MPa and 30°C for 3 h, then the temperature was increased to 60°C and kept for 1.5 h. Finally, the temperature was increased further to 80°C for another 1.5 h. Post-curing was done by releasing the pressure while maintaining the temperature at 80°C for 18 h, then it was reduced to 60°C for an additional 3 h before allowing the laminate to cool down to room temperature before creating the test specimens.

Mechanical Property Analyses

The resulting FRP laminates were cut into test sample sizes and subjected to the appropriate ASTM methods for measuring flexural and tensile properties: the three-point bending tests (ASTM D790M) were done using Shimadzu Autograph AGS-J-1kN Universal Testing Machine, while the tensile tests were done using Shimadzu Autograph DCS-R5000 Universal Testing Machine. Also, surface characterization to study the effects of alkali fiber treatment, as well as the fracture surface after conducting the strength tests, was done by scanning electron microscopy using SEM (JEOL JSM-5310LV Scanning Microscope).

Figure 3. SEM micrographs of abaca fiber at different alkali treatment periods.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Chemical modification of natural fiber reinforcements is essential in improving the interfacial bonding between the fiber and the matrix. It has already been reported that alkali treatment or mercerization is considered to be a good technique for overcoming the shortcomings of natural fiber-reinforced composites, such as high moisture absorption and poor fiber-matrix adhesion. When subjected to alkali treatment, the lignin, hemicellulose, and water-soluble components, as well as other natural impurities, are removed from cellulose backbone. This effect results to disentanglement and exposure of cellulose fibrils, which provides more venues for mechanical interlocking between the fiber and the polymer matrix. Moreover, the mechanical interlocking is further promoted by the scalding of the fiber surface when it was alkali treated at an elevated temperature, causing an increase in fiber surface roughness.

Another function of the alkali treatment is to activate the hydroxyl groups of the cellulose, according to the general reaction

Activation of these hydroxyl groups decreases the hydrophilicity of the cellulose, making them more thermodynamically compatible with the polymer resin and thus improving the fiber-matrix interfacial adhesion [12].

Figure 4. Comparison of the tensile and flexural strengths between the untreated and treated abaca/furan composites (at 8wt% fiber loading).

The effect of chemical modification on natural fibers may vary depending primarily on the extent at which the fibers are subjected to [13]. It has already been reported that the length of alkali treatment period significantly affects the performance of the NFR composites [14]. Longer treatment period provides more time to remove the lignin and hemicelluloses that binds the cellulose fibrils and gives the desired effect; however, the reaction of cellulose with the alkali also includes the conversion of crystalline cellulose into amorphous cellulose, which decreases the fiber strength, and excessive treatment may cause fiber degradation, resulting to an adverse effect in the mechanical properties of both the fiber (as shown in Figure 3) and the composite. From the micrographs shown, it may be concluded that the optimum alkali treatment for continuous abaca fibers using 5wt% NaOH at 80°C is about 9 hours; at longer treatment periods, cellulose conversion would occur in extreme, and the fiber integrity would be compromised.

Figure 4 shows the effect of alkali treatment on the abaca/furan composite. As expected, the mechanical strength of the furan FRP with treated abaca is higher compared to that of untreated abaca composite. This is because of the improved interfacial bonding between the furan matrix and the treated abaca fibers. The raw abaca fibers exhibit extremely poor furan wettability that results to poor adhesion.

Figure 5. Flexural properties of abaca/furan green composites at various fiber loading.

The effect of fiber loading on the performance of abaca/furan composites are shown in Figure 5. The flexural properties are observed to decrease at increasing fiber fractions, since there is an expected increase in the weak interfacial area between the fiber and the matrix, which, consequently, decreases the strength [15]. The weak interfacial areas can be attributed to the void spaces formed in the fiber sheet regions that experience the least amount of polymer wetting. This effect has overcome the reinforcing value of the highly rigid abaca fibers, which suffer a loss of polymer wetting due to their dense proximity with each other, both within and with other fiber sheets. Another possible cause of rigidity loss is the removal of the lignin and hemicelluloses from the abaca fibers during alkali treatment.

As seen from the micrographs in Figure 6, fiber pull-out in the fracture surface occurs to some extent in certain areas, which is indicative of weak adhesion at the fiber-matrix interface due to poor wetting. Based on the results obtained, it may be concluded that while the alkali treatment may significantly improve fiber-matrix adhesion, its effect seems insufficient to successfully fabricate a long abaca fiber, furan resin-based green composite with the desired mechanical performance; additional chemical modification must be applied on the natural fiber to achieve this objective.

Figure 6. SEM micrographs of the bending fracture surface of abaca/furan composite.

CONCLUSION

Based on the initial results of this research, the following conclusion may be drawn:

1. The application of bio-based furan resin for fabricating RTP laminates involves a very sensitive procedure that requires careful consideration of the complications arising from furan's curing kinetics.
2. In the manufacture of continuous abaca fiber-reinforced green composites, the fibers require about 9 hours of hot alkali treatment at high temperature (80°C) for optimum cellulose fibril exposure with minimum fiber damage.
3. While alkali treatment does improve the fiber-matrix interfacial, additional chemical modifications may still be needed to allow the production of continuous abaca/furan composites with satisfactory mechanical performance at high fiber loading.

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